

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOTUBE /EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATES PROCESSED USING PREPREG METHOD

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the processing and mechanical properties of aligned MWCNT /epoxy lamina and laminates processed using a hot-melt prepreg method. On-axis and off-axis tensile tests (0°, 45°, 90°) of aligned CNT/epoxy lamina specimens were carried out, and the elastic moduli, E_{11} , E_{22} , and G_{12} were obtained. Fracture surfaces of lamina specimens after tensile testing were observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). As a result, pulled-out CNTs without epoxy adhesion were observed at the interface, which suggests the weak interfacial shear/tensile strengths at the interface between CNT and epoxy. CNT/epoxy laminates ([0°/90°]s, [60°/0°/-60°]s, [0°/45°/90°/-45°]s) were successfully fabricated using aligned CNT/epoxy prepreg sheets. The CNT volume fraction was approximately 10%. No visible void and delamination were observed in composite laminates, and the thickness of each layer was almost the same as that of prepreg. The Young's modulus of CNT/epoxy laminates agreed with the theoretical values, which were calculated using classical laminate theory (CLT) and elastic moduli of CNT/epoxy lamina. The failure strain of [0°/90°]s, [60°/0°/-60°]s, and [0°/45°/90°/-45°]s laminates is respectively 0.65%, 0.92%, 0.63%, which are higher than that of 0° composite lamina (0.5%). The result suggests that the failure strain of 0° layer in composite laminates is improved due to other layers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Basic technology for making horizontally aligned carbon nanotube sheets has been established by pulling out CNTs from vertically grown carbon nanotube array (forest) to horizontal direction [1-4]. Aligned CNT sheets are attractive for the reinforcement of composite materials, therefore a lot of researches regarding aligned CNT/polymer composites have been carried out [5-16]. As results, it has been understood that aligned-CNT/polymer matrix composites has excellent mechanical properties as compared with "conventional" randomly oriented CNT /polymer composites.

The authors proposed a simple and easy method to make aligned CNT/ polymer composites using prepreg [10]. The process is the same as that for continuous fiber composites such as carbon fiber reinforced plastics composites (CFRP). The advantages of the processing method have been demonstrated in previous papers [10, 12, 15, 16]. Aligned CNT/epoxy prepreg has a lot of advantages in alignment, volume fraction, handling, and processability. The prepreg process is easy to apply to mass production. Stacking prepreg sheets to arbitrary directions, tailored CNT/epoxy composite structures as well as materials are easily fabricated. Not only mechanical properties but

electrical/thermal properties (incl. thermal expansion) can be flexibly engineered. In addition to autoclave curing, press molding is applicable because of discontinuous reinforcements, therefore fabrications of complex and small components are expected to be much easier as compared with continuous fiber composites. The aligned CNT/epoxy composites have no sharp interface between laminae. Therefore the damage tolerance against out-of plane impact loading is expected to be better than that of carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates. This suggests that robust composites can be achieved. However, the experimental results on the mechanical properties of aligned CNT/polymer composite laminates have not been reported.

This study examined the mechanical properties of aligned CNT /epoxy composite laminates processed using a hot-melt prepreg method. On-axis and off-axis tensile tests for CNT/epoxy composite laminae were carried out to evaluate the elastic moduli (E_{11} , E_{22} , and G_{12}). CNT/epoxy composite laminates ($[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$, $[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$, $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$) are fabricated, and mechanical properties are evaluated using tensile testing. The experimental results are discussed in detail.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Starting materials

Multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) array (forest) used in this study was made using chemical vapor deposition (CVD). Inoue et al. successfully established an easy and efficient synthesis method for making vertically aligned long MWCNTs (array) using iron chloride powders as a catalyst [3, 4]. The MWCNTs of which length exceeds 1 mm were successfully grown using a conventional thermal chemical vapor deposition (CVD) on a bare quartz substrate with the single gas flow of C_2H_2 gas only for 20 min. In addition to such a high growth rate, well-aligned MWCNT sheets are easily made from the MWCNT forest by pulling it out. The detailed procedure for the fabrications of CNT arrays and sheets was reported elsewhere [3, 4]. Figure 1(a) and (b) show an optical and scanning electron micrographs (SEM) illustrating horizontally aligned CNT sheet. Although most of CNTs are aligned, waviness and entanglement are also observed. The CNT sheets are not perfectly aligned. The diameter and length are in the range of 50-70 nm, and 1-2 mm, therefore the aspect ratio is extremely high ($> 10,000$).

B-stage cured epoxy resin with release paper was obtained from a commercial prepreg company. The epoxy resin consists of bisphenol-A type epoxy, novolac type epoxy, and aromatic diamine curing agent, and the recommended cure condition is $130^\circ C$ for 1.5 h. The areal weight of epoxy resin film is well controlled as 30 g/m^2 , and the thickness is approximately 25 μm .

Figure 1: Optical and SEM micrographs of horizontal aligned CNT sheet

2.2 Processing of CNT/epoxy composite laminae and laminates

CNT/epoxy composite laminae and laminates were made using prepreg method [10]. A schematic drawing for the process is shown in Fig. 2. A CNT sheet, which has 20 mm width and 95 mm length was put on a polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) sheet (thickness 2 mm), and covered with epoxy resin film with a release paper. Epoxy resin was impregnated into the CNT sheet at $90^\circ C$ for 3 min between

steel plates of a hot press. It was easy to peel off the prepreg with a release paper from the PTFE sheet. The thickness of prepreg sheets, which depends on the CNT areal weight, is in the range of 24–48 μm . The prepreg had good drapability and tackiness. CNT loading was well controlled by changing the CNT areal weight.

Figure 2: Schematic drawing showing the processing of CNT/Epoxy laminae and laminates

Figure 3: Specimen and test rig used for tensile testing of CNT/epoxy laminae and laminates

After peeling off a prepreg sheet from a release paper, the prepreg sheet was cured at 130°C for 1.5 h under 2 MPa in a hot press. Three kinds of composite laminae, 0° 45° and 90° were made for on-axis and off-axis tensile testing. In addition to this, three kinds of composite laminates, [0°/90°]_s, [60°/0°/-60°]_s, and [0°/45°/90°/-45°]_s, were made. Although the target CNT volume fraction was 10 vol. %, the CNT volume fraction values of resultant laminates were slightly different each other.

2.3 Characterizations

The microstructure of composites was observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, S-4700, Hitachi, Japan). CNT weight fraction was determined using a thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA, TGA-6300, SII, Japan). Each specimen was heated up to 800°C under a constant heating rate of 10°C/min in argon (300 ml/min). The CNT volume fraction was calculated using density of CNT, and epoxy ($\rho_{\text{Epoxy}} = 1.2 \text{ g/cm}^3$). The CNT density was unknown, therefore it was assumed to be 2 g/cm³.

Tensile tests were conducted on a screw-driven mechanical testing machine (Model 5966, Instron, USA) with a 1 KN load cell under a constant displacement rate of 0.2 mm/min at room temperature (25 C). Specimen size was 24-48 μm thick, 3 mm width, and 90 mm overall length. The thickness was carefully measured using an SEM micrographs after tensile testing. Aluminum end tabs (40 mm length, 3 mm thick) were bonded on both sides of the grip portions as shown in Fig.3 (a). The distance between tabs is 30 mm. Longitudinal-strain was measured using a non-contacting video extensometer (AVE, Instron, USA). Two pieces of white paper were bonded on the specimen as target marker of gauge length (15 mm).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Mechanical properties of composite laminae (on-axis and off-axis tensile testing)

CNT weight fraction, CNT volume fraction, thickness and number of tensile specimens of CNT/epoxy laminae (0°, 45°, 90°), and laminates ([0°/90°]_s, [60°/0°/-60°]_s, [0°/45°/90°/-45°]_s) are presented in Table 1. CNT volume fraction measured using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), was 5-35 vol.% for 0 specimens, 10-25 vol.% for 45° and 90° specimens, and approximately 10 vol.% for laminates ([0°/90°]_s, [60°/0°/-60°]_s, [0°/45°/90°/-45°]_s). The result suggests that the effect of CNT volume fraction must be taken into consideration for discussing the mechanical properties of composite lamina and laminates.

Table1 Average CNT loading and thickness of CNT/epoxy lamina and laminate

	Aligned CNT-sheet orientation angle [°]	CNT loading		Thickness [mm]	Number of specimen
		M_f [wt.%]	V_f [vol.%]		
Epoxy	-	-	-	-	2
ML-0-#1	0°	7.3	4.5	24-25	3
ML-0-#2		19.4	12.6	27-29	4
ML-0-#3		25.5	17.1	27-37	7
ML-0-#4		31.8	21.9	32-35	6
ML-0-#5		36.1	25.3	32-43	5
ML-0-#6		45.9	33.7	41-48	5
ML-45-#1	45°	15.1	9.64	25-35	3
ML-45-#2		28.2	19.1	30-35	3
ML-90-#1	90°	17.9	11.6	28-33	3
ML-90-#2		35.6	24.9	27-34	4
[0/90] _s	[0°/90°] _s	17.0	10.9	107-117	4
[60/0/-60] _s	[60°/0°/-60°] _s	14.8	9.45	153-189	3
[0/45/90/-45] _s	[0°/45°/90°/-45°] _s	16.5	10.6	215-245	4

Typical stress-strain curves of CNT/epoxy composite laminae of which V_f is approximately 10 vol.% are presented in Fig. 4, and the average values of Young's modulus, ultimate tensile strength,

and failure strain are summarized in Table 2. Figure 5 shows the relation between CNT volume fraction (V_f) and Young's modulus. Anisotropic elastic properties are clearly observed. The experimental results suggest that the relation between CNT volume fraction and Young's modulus (E_{11} , E_{45} , E_{22}) is almost linear as follows;

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= 228V_f + 2.5 \\ E_{45} &= 34.1V_f + 2.5 \\ E_{22} &= 13.9V_f + 2.5 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The unit of elastic moduli is GPa. When the CNT volume fraction is normalized as 10 vol.%, the elastic moduli of CNT/epoxy lamina are estimated to be $E_{11} = 25.3$ GPa, and $E_{22} = 3.9$ GPa. Shear modulus, G_{12} is calculated using E_{11} , E_{45} , E_{22} , and Poisson's ratio ν_{12} for a transversely anisotropic material.

$$G_{12} = 1/(4/E_{45} - 1/E_{11} - 1/E_{22} + 2\nu_{12}/E_{11}) \quad (2)$$

It is difficult to measure the Poisson's ratio of a film specimen, ν_{12} is assumed as 0.3, which is a typical value for polymer. As a result, the shear modulus G_{12} is estimated to be 2.5 GPa for $V_f=10$ vol.%. The ratio E_{22}/E_{11} , and G_{12}/E_{11} are respectively 0.15 and 0.1, the CNT/epoxy composite lamina has considerable anisotropic elastic properties.

The elastic moduli of unidirectional carbon fiber /epoxy composites (IM600/133, $V_f = 55$ vol.%, Toho Tenax, Japan) are $E_{11} = 152$ GPa, $E_{22} = 8.2$ GPa, $G_{12} = 4.2$ GPa [17]. Therefore, The ratio E_{22}/E_{11} and G_{12}/E_{11} of IM600/133 are respectively 0.05, and 0.03, while E_{22}/E_{11} and G_{12}/E_{11} of CNT/epoxy composite (normalized as $V_f=0.55$) are 0.08, and 0.09. The anisotropic elastic property of CNT/epoxy is less significant. This is due to the scatter in CNT orientation angles in the composites [12, 15].

Figure 4: Typical stress-strain curves of CNT/epoxy lamina (0°, 45°, 90°)

Figure 5: Young's modulus vs CNT volume fraction of CNT/epoxy lamina (0°, 45°, 90°)

Fracture-surfaces after tensile testing were observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, S-4700, Hitachi, Japan). SEM micrographs are shown in Fig. 6. In the case of 0° specimens (Fig.6 (a) (d)), pulled-out CNTs perpendicular to the fracture surface are clearly observed. Small holes, which are opposite side of pulled-out CNT, are also visible. For 45° lamina specimens (Fig.6 (b) (e)), CNTs are also pulled out to oblique directions. It implies that the debonding at the interface between CNT and epoxy occurs before the final failure of composites due to weak interface shear stress [15]. In addition to this, pulled-out CNTs in parallel with a fracture surface are visible in 90° lamina specimens (Fig.6 (c) (f)). Epoxy resin adhesion on pulled-out CNT surfaces is not observed. The tensile strength of 90° specimen (11.6 vol.%) is 43 MPa, which is much inferior to that of epoxy resin (55 MPa). The result implies that the strength of 90° lamina specimen is mainly governed by the interface tensile strength between CNT and epoxy.

Table 2 Average Young's modulus, tensile strength and failure strain of aligned CNT/Epoxy composite lamina (0° , 45° , 90°)

	CNT volume fraction, V_f [vol.%]	Young's modulus [GPa]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Fracture strain [%]
Epoxy	0	2.5	54.7	3.05
ML-0-#1	4.5	18.8	97.4	0.503
ML-0-#2	12.6	27.8	153	0.545
ML-0-#3	17.1	40.8	217	0.541
ML-0-#4	21.9	55.7	249	0.457
ML-0-#5	25.3	64.9	317	0.489
ML-0-#6	33.7	73.3	344	0.477
ML-45-#1	9.64	5.24	65.4	1.54
ML-45-#2	19.1	9.26	57.4	0.596
ML-90-#1	11.6	4.01	43.3	1.25
ML-90-#2	24.9	6.01	58.3	0.905

Figure 6: SEM micrographs showing fracture surfaces of aligned CNT/Epoxy composite laminae after tensile testing, (a) 0° , (b) 45° , (c) 90° and high magnification of (d) 0° , (e) 45° , 90° .

3.2 Mechanical properties of composite laminates

Typical stress-strain curves of CNT/epoxy laminates ($[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$, $[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$, $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$) are presented in Fig. 7. Stress-strain curves of 0° , 45° , and 90° lamina specimens are superimposed in Fig. 7. The average values of Young's modulus, ultimate tensile strength, and failure strain are summarized in Table 3. Tensile strength of each laminate is approximately 100 MPa, which is independent of the stacking sequence.

Figure 7: Typical stress-strain curves of CNT/epoxy laminates ($[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$, $[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$, $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$) and laminae (0° , 45° , 90°)

Figure 9: Young's modulus of composite laminates calculated using classical laminate theory as a function of CNT volume fraction

Table3 Average Young's modulus, tensile strength and failure strain of CNT/Epoxy composite laminates ($[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$, $[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$, $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$)

Stacking sequence	CNT volume fraction V_f [vol.%]	Young's modulus [GPa]	Theoretical Young's Modulus [GPa]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Fracture strain [%]
$[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$	10.9	17.1	15.1	109	0.65
$[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$	9.45	12.0	11.2	110	0.92
$[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$	10.6	14.5	13.4	94.2	0.63

Table4 Average thickness of each layer in CNT/Epoxy composite laminates

	Thickness [μm]
$[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$	$t_0 = 26, t_{90} = 30$
$[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$	$t_0 = 25, t_{60} = 31, t_{-60} = 32$
$[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$	$t_0 = 27, t_{45} = 28, t_{-45} = 33, t_{90} = 26$

* The thickness was measured from SEM micrographs

SEM micrographs after tensile tests are shown in Fig.8 . Figure 8(d)-(f) are high magnification SEM micrographs of each laminate. Void and delamination are not visible at the interlayer. The thickness of each layer, which is measured from SEM micrographs, is approximately $30 \mu\text{m}$. This value is almost the same as that of lamina specimen (0° , 45° , 90°). CNT/epoxy laminates, which have arbitrary stacking sequence can be easily fabricated using prepreg, and the quality is quite good. Fracture surfaces of each layer (0° , 45° , 90°) in laminate specimens ($[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$, $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$) seem to be almost the same as those of lamina specimen (0° , 45° , 90°).

The failure strain of $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminate is 0.65 %, whereas that of 0° lamina specimen is 0.54 %. The experimental result suggests that 90° layers affect the tensile strength of $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminate. One of the possible phenomenon is suppression of matrix cracking and debonding at the CNT/matrix interface in 0° layers. The interface shear strengths (IFSS) between CNT and epoxy must be weak because of significant pulled-out CNT at the fracture surface as shown in Fig. 6. Weak IFSS causes debonding at the interface before the final failure, resulting in matrix crack and splitting crack propagation [19, 20]. The 90° layers may suppress splitting crack propagation in 0° layers. The similar

discussion can be made for $[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$ laminate. The failure strain is 0.92 %. It implies that the stress in 0° layers is not 100 MPa but approximately 230 MPa. Further investigation about the failure and damage behavior of CNT/epoxy composites is necessary to understand the phenomenon.

The Young's modulus of CNT/epoxy laminate specimens is estimated using classical laminate theory (CLT) and elastic moduli of lamina (Table 1). The thickness of each layer t_θ , was directly measured from SEM micrographs, and the results are summarized in Table 4. The theoretical values are shown in Table 3. They have good agreement with the experimental values with an uncertainty of 14%. This suggests that CNT/epoxy laminates can be treated as conventional composite laminates, and CLT is effective for rough estimation of elastic moduli.

The effect of CNT volume fraction on the Young's modulus of CNT/epoxy laminates ($[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$, $[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$, $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$) was examined using the numerical results based on CLT. The results are presented in Fig. 9 as a function of CNT volume fraction. The typical Young's modulus of quasi-isotropic CFRP ($[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$, $V_f = 50 \sim 60$ vol.%) is 50 – 55 GPa. To achieve 50 GPa of Young's modulus, the CNT volume fraction should be 39, 47, and 47 vol.% for $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$, $[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$, $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$, composite laminates. Although the maximum CNT volume fraction in our study is approximately 40 %, it is possible to increase the CNT volume fraction by improving the process. In addition to this, stretching treatment for CNT sheet or prepreg is effective to improve the scattering in CNT orientation angles, resulting in higher Young's modulus [9,15]. In conclusion, aligned CNT/epoxy laminate composites possess almost the same capability as compared with CFRP from the view point of elastic properties (elastic modulus).

Figure 8: SEM micrographs showing fracture surfaces of CNT/Epoxy composite laminate after tensile testing; (a) $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$, (b) $[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$, (c) $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$, and high magnification micrographs around the interlayer; (d) $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$, (e) $[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$, (f) $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the processing and mechanical properties of aligned MWCNT /epoxy lamina and laminates processed using a hot-melt prepreg method. The following conclusions were made.

1. On-axis and off-axis tensile tests (0° , 45° , 90°) of aligned CNT/epoxy lamina specimens were carried out, and the elastic moduli, E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} were estimated.
2. Fracture surfaces of lamina specimens after tensile testing were observed using a scanning

electron microscope (SEM). As a result, pulled-out CNTs without epoxy adhesion were observed at the interface, which suggests the weak interfacial shear/tensile strengths at the interface between CNT and epoxy.

3. CNT/epoxy laminates ($[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$, $[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$, $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$) were successfully fabricated using aligned CNT/epoxy prepreg sheets. The CNT volume fraction was approximately 10%. No visible void and delamination were observed in composite laminates, and the thickness of each layer was almost the same as that of prepreg. The Young's modulus of CNT/epoxy laminates agreed with the theoretical values, which were calculated using classical laminate theory (CLT) and elastic moduli of CNT/epoxy lamina.
4. The failure strain of $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$, $[60^\circ/0^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$, and $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$ laminates is respectively 0.65%, 0.92%, 0.63%, which are higher than that of 0° composite lamina (0.5%). The result suggests that the failure strain of 0° layer in composite laminates is improved due to other layers.

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